

OHDSI IRELAND WORKSHOP

FOUNDATIONS IN OMOP AND REAL-WORLD DATA:
HOW TO RUN YOUR FIRST REAL-WORLD STUDY

26TH JANUARY, 2026

14.30– 17:30

WORKSHOP LEADERS:

Dr Stelios Theophanis
Real-World Data Analyst,
University of Leeds, UK

Professor Geoff Hall
Professor of Digital
Health, University of
Leeds UK

Dr Catherine Mahoney
Senior Advisor-HEOR &
RWE Scientist, Eli Lilly

Part 1: Introduction to OHDSI Tools and Cohort Creation

Welcome & Clinical Context

OMOP CDM Essentials

Vocabularies & Athena Exploration

Building the Cancer Cohort

Cohort Diagnostics & Refinement

Part 2: OMOP and RWE in Practice

The Clinician's Perspective

OMOP in Oncology

Workshop Summary & Resources